

Polymetallic Complexes. Part-XXXV. Complexes of Manganese-, Cobalt-, Nickel-, Copper-, Cadmium- and Mercury(II) with Chelating OO-OO Donor Azo Dye Ligand, 4,4'-Bis[5-(1-formyl-2-hydroxyphenyl)azo]diphenyl

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In continuation of our earlier study, the present communication reports the preparation and characterisation of a new bis-bidentate azo ligand and its seven metal complexes.

Results and Discussion

The complexes have the compositions $[M_2LCl_2(H_2O)_6]$ and $[M'_2LCl_2(H_2O)_2]$, where $M = Mn^{II}$, Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} ; $M' = Zn^{II}$, Cd^{II} , Hg^{II} , $LH_2 = 4,4'$ -bis[5-(1-formyl-2-hydroxyphenyl)azo]diphenyl. The complexes are quite stable at room temperature and even up to 120° indicate coordinated nature of the water molecules. All the complexes are amorphous in nature having high melting points and insoluble in common organic solvents but sparingly soluble in DMF. Low Λ_M values ($4.7-5.8 \Omega^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1}$) indicate non-electrolytic nature of the complexes.

The principal ir bands of the ligands are observed at $1665 (C=O)$, $1612 (N=N)$ and $1533 cm^{-1} (C=O \text{ phenolic})$. The shifting of the first and third bands to lower frequency regions is observed in the metal chelates indicating bonding of the ligand to the metal ions through carbonyl and phenolic oxygen atoms respectively. The band appearing due to $-N=N-$ group does not undergo any change in the metal complexes showing non-coordination of azo nitrogen atoms to the metal ions¹. The presence of coordinated water molecules in all the metal complexes is indicated by the appearance of a broad band at $\sim 3450 cm^{-1}$ followed by a sharp band $\sim 840 cm^{-1}$ assignable to OH stretching and rocking vibrations respectively. The conclusive evidence of bonding of oxygen atoms is provided by the appearance of ν_{M-O} band at $\sim 425 cm^{-1}$.

The electronic spectrum of the Mn^{II} complex exhibits four bands at 18 450, 22 270, 24 460 and 27 350 cm^{-1} assignable to ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g} (G)$, $\rightarrow {}^4T_{2g} (G)$, $\rightarrow {}^4E_g$ and $\rightarrow {}^4T_{2g} (D)$ transitions respectively, in octahedral stereochemistry². The electronic spectrum of the Co^{II} complex shows three $d-d$ transitions at 8 895, 17 850 and 21 550 cm^{-1} attributable to ${}^4T_{1g} (F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g} (F)$, $\rightarrow {}^4A_{2g} (F)$ and $\rightarrow {}^4T_{1g} (P)$ respectively. The ligand field parameters like Dq (889 cm^{-1}), B (847.6 cm^{-1}), $\beta_{3/5}$ (0.87), ν_2/ν_1 (2.0) and σ (14.55) suggest an octahedral geometry around the metal ions. The Ni^{II} complex reveals three bands at 11 750, 18 320 and 28 650 cm^{-1} assignable to ${}^3A_{2g} (F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g} (F)$, $\rightarrow {}^3T_{1g} (F)$ and $\rightarrow {}^3T_{1g} (P)$ transitions respectively. The values of Dq (657 cm^{-1}), B (781.3 cm^{-1}), $\beta_{3/5}$ (0.75), ν_2/ν_1 (1.56) and σ (33.33) are in agreement with an octahedral geometry for the complex³. The Cu^{II} complex displays a broad asymmetric ligand field band in the region 13 330–15 600 cm^{-1} with the maxima at 14 430 cm^{-1} , assignable to ${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$ transition in a distorted-octahedral stereochemistry⁴.

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				
		M	C	H	N	Cl
LH_2	Reddish yellow	—	68.5 (69.3)	3.6 4.0	12.1 12.44	15.2 15.78
$[Co_2LCl_2(H_2O)_6]$	Yellow	15.2 (15.8)	41.5 41.9	3.2 3.7	7.4 7.5	9.4 9.5
$[Ni_2LCl_2(H_2O)_6]$	Light brown	15.1 (15.7)	41.2 41.9	3.2 3.7	7.2 7.5	9.2 9.5
$[Cu_2LCl_2(H_2O)_6]$	Leafy green	16.4 (16.8)	40.5 41.3	3.5 3.7	7.1 7.4	8.9 9.4
$[Zn_2LCl_2(H_2O)_2]$	Brown	18.5 (19.0)	44.8 45.5	2.6 2.9	7.7 8.1	9.8 10.3
$[Cd_2LCl_2(H_2O)_2]$	Reddish yellow	28.3 (28.8)	39.5 40.0	2.2 2.5	6.5 7.1	8.6 9.1
$[Hg_2LCl_2(H_2O)_2]$	White	40.7 (41.9)	31.8 32.6	1.9 2.0	5.3 5.8	7.1 7.4
$[Mn_2LCl_2(H_2O)_6]$	Dark brown	14.2 (14.9)	2.1 2.3	3.4 3.8	7.2 7.6	9.2 9.6

The Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Ag^{II} complexes are four-coordinated with a tetrahedral configuration around the metal ions based on analytical and ir spectral data.

The following structure can be suggested tentatively for the complexes.

$M = Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}; X = H_2O$
 $M = Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Hg^{II}; X = \text{nil}.$

Experimental

The bis-azo dye was prepared by the coupling reaction of the diazonium chloride obtained from benzidine with the alkaline solution of salicylaldehyde at 0–5°.

The metal complexes were prepared by adding ethanolic solution of metal chlorides separately to the ligand solution in ethanol in 2 : 1 molar ratio. The mixture was warmed over a water bath for 0.5 h, then cooled. pH of the solution was raised to ~7 and the resulting metal complexes were washed with ethanol, ether and dried under reduced pressure.

Elemental analyses were performed by standard procedures. Conductance was measured in $10^{-2} M$ DMF solution and magnetic susceptibility at room temperature by Gouy method. In spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 398 spectrophotometer and electronic spectra ($10^{-2} M$ DMF) on a Hilger and Watt uvispeck spectrophotometer.

References

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